

D9.5: Innovation Management Plan

Authors: Rosemarie Bernabe

Editor: Søren Holm

Responsible Open Science in Europe

ROSIE

Grant Agreement no.:101006430

Lead contractor for this deliverable: University of Oslo

Deliverable factsheet:

Project Number:	101006430
Project Acronym:	ROSIE
Project Title:	Responsible Open Science in Europe
Title of Deliverable:	
Work Package:	WP9
Due date according to contract:	31.08.21
Editor(s):	Rosemarie Bernabe
Contributor(s):	Søren Holm, Vivian Mbanya
Reviewer(s):	Rosemarie Bernabe
Approved by	Søren Holm

Abbreviation	OS: open science; RE: research ethics; RI: research integrity; LMICs: Low-medium countries
---------------------	--

Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	Austrian Agency for Research Integrity	OeAWi	Austria
3.	Partner	European Citizen Science Association	ECSA	Germany
4.	Partner	European Network of Research Ethics Committees	EUREC	Germany
5.	Partner	Federation of Finnish Learned Societies	TSV	Finland
6.	Partner	High Council for the Evaluation of Research and Higher Education	Hceres	France
7.	Partner	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment	INRAEe	France
8.	Partner	National Technical University of Athens	NTUA	Greece
9.	Partner	Universidade Católica Portuguesa	UCP	Portugal
10.	Partner	University of Latvia	UL	Latvia
11.	Partner	University of Tartu	UT	Estonia
12.	Partner	University of Southeastern Norway	USN	Norway

Revision history:

VERSION	DATE	Revised by	Reason
0.1	30.07.21		1 st Draft
1.0	30.08.21		Final version

Table of contents

1	Introduction	5
2	Innovation management plan	5
2.1	Purpose of the deliverable.....	5
2.2	Sustainability and knowledge sharing.....	6
2.2.1	Training materials	6
2.2.2	Sustainability planning	6

1 Introduction

ROSiE is a project supported by Horizon 2020. Its purpose includes creating innovative, useful tools in collaboration with all relevant parties in order to promote ethical open science (OS) and citizen science. Keeping with this vision, one of the goals of the ROSiE project is to make sure the project is managed effectively. Realizing the innovation management plan for the ROSiE project is Work Package 9 deliverable 9.5. To fulfill this deliverable, we have created a strategic plan on how to foster the novel product created in the ROSiE project.

Our perspective is to share our resources to reach the target audience in order to maximize the impact of ROSiE. We want to extend our innovative products beyond academia. ROSiE will produce sustainable digital learning resources i.e. online training tools and the knowledge Hub to benefit stakeholders and potential users.

2 Innovation management plan

This section describes the innovation management processes for the online training tools materials and the knowledge Hub. The section also provides the purpose of the deliverable.

2.1 Purpose of the deliverable

This WP9 deliverable is within the tasks of Work Package 9, and it intends to fulfill outlines the ROSiE the plans through the for the dissemination and transfer of innovative knowledge and products that ROSiE will develop from the ROSiE project, during and ideally beyond the lifetime of the project.

2.2 Sustainability and knowledge sharing

The Knowledge Hub (KH) will provide all OS actors (existing and future platforms, decision makers, etc.) with customized solutions. The KH, designed and governed to ensure its sustainability beyond the end of ROSiE, will support all research disciplines in actively pursuing open approaches in science and research while complying with legal frameworks and ethical standards.

2.2.1 Training materials

ROSiE will produce online and traditional training materials for responsible OS for students, young, and experienced researchers and citizen scientists. To ensure sustainability, the training materials will form part of the training e-platform created by European Network of Research Ethics and Research Integrity (ENERI) and hosted by the European Commission platform SINAPSE. These training materials will also be made available on appropriate open access platforms, including the knowledge Hub, the ROSiE website, and the Embassy of Good Science, and they will be distributed under an appropriate, non-restrictive open access license.

2.2.2 Sustainability planning

NTUA, with the close cooperation of ECSA, OeAWI and UiO, will organize at M34 a Next Steps Conference. This conference will address the continuous impact of ROSiE, by disseminating the project's outcomes and paving the way for its future use, by informing relevant stakeholders on the functionalities of the ROSiE platform. A training workshop for ROSiE platform will also be included in the agenda of the Next Steps Conference, with the cooperation of OeAWI.

- Establish an “expertise pool”, collaborating with the ENERI e-Community and The Embassy of Good Science (depending on its function by the time of the 3rd year of ROSiE application, i.e. in which it will have become a wiki platform)
- Maintain the ROSiE website and social media channels for 3 years after the completion of the project.

